

SOCIO-ECONOMIC CONDITION OF RURAL YOUTH AND WAYS TO IMPROVE IT

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Abstract: The lifestyle of rural youth is determined by socio-economic, political, domestic, psychological factors, but unlike that of urban youth, it was difficult for rural residents to adapt to new conditions, which affected the content of the socialization of the young generation. If we pay attention to the data of sociological surveys, the deep socio-economic crisis in the village has a negative effect on the formation of values in the youth of the village, it leads to the spread of some negative processes in the environment of the youth.

Key words: Rural youth, creating living conditions, preventing unemployment, vocational training, reducing poverty, creating job vacancies.

The lifestyle of rural youth is determined by socio-economic, political, domestic, and psychological factors, but unlike that of urban youth, it has some unique characteristics. If we turn to history, the economic reforms of the second half of the 1980s and the beginning of the 1990s led to the depression of agricultural production and a sharp decrease in the standard of living for rural areas. The countryside has become one of the most vulnerable sectors of the economy. Although the ideas of civil society included in the change processes in the village had a positive effect, there were also negative situations.

These negative situations include a decrease in reproductive function, deterioration of physical health, socio-psychological condition, lack of confidence in the future, unemployment, and a decrease in the content of leisure activities. According to the sociological survey conducted in 2019, most of the rural youth are experiencing financial difficulties. Only 7% of the 200 surveyed village youth said that they did not feel the need for anything; 25.5% are satisfied with their material situation to one degree or another; 59.2% are worried about their future. The reason for this is determined by the limited or non-existence of opportunities for personal realization of the youth in the village during work and non-work time. Job vacancies, wages, opportunities to organize recreation do not match the interests, needs and life plans of young people. In some remote villages, highly qualified specialists who have returned with a high level of education do not have the opportunity to work in their specialty and receive a salary commensurate with the level of their qualifications.

A large part of rural youth cannot find a job not only in their own village, but also in the district center or a nearby city. Therefore, many young people, even those with higher education, go to work abroad. 69.8% of respondents are worried about the poverty of rural areas [2]. It can be said that these reasons are the reason for the decrease in the birth rate in the villages. In the former Soviet era, rural youth went to work at the age of 18 and returned at the age of 20. Young families would have at least 4-5 children. Some families had 7-9 or more children. Due to the fact that these children grew up and started families, despite the migration, that is, the migration of people of other nationalities to their historical homelands, the population of Uzbekistan increased. Today, most young families in the village have 1-3 children. The complex socio-economic situation in the countryside also causes young people to move to the city. In recent years, many positive things have been done in our country in terms of providing employment to young people. These include supporting young farmers and private entrepreneurs, providing loans for homesteads, establishing various cluster enterprises, etc. Today, creating conditions for living in rural areas (building model houses, supporting entrepreneurship) is one of the first priority tasks for improving the agricultural economy. However, the lack of start-up capital, equipment, and partners leads to abandonment of entrepreneurship and farming. In addition, the processes of criminalization are affecting the minds of rural youth. In the eyes of the young generation, cases such as tax evasion, military service avoidance, and misappropriation of found things have become commonplace.

The mass media, first of all, the Internet, have a negative impact on the legal consciousness and behavior of young people. There are a lot of movies on the Internet showing or detailing the ways and methods of committing a crime. The fact that it is normal for the "heroes" who follow the principles of "an eye for an eye, a tooth for a tooth, a soul for a soul" in war movies to use any means and methods to achieve their goals has a negative impact on the minds of young people. In recent years, the closure of cinemas, libraries, clubs, clubs, and sports fields in villages has severely affected the socio-cultural environment of the village. All this reduced the range of choices of the forms of recreation and free time useful for rural youth.

The free time and leisure time of young people is fun, unorganized, individual and personal. The lack of conditions for enjoying leisure time among young people leads to loneliness, disunity, disconnection from each other, culturally and educationally lagging behind urban youth. The lack of opportunity to spend and organize free time meaningfully, qualitatively, usefully, financial difficulties, unemployment, the realization that there is no way to change life for the better can lead to the spread of negative diseases in the environment of rural youth. In order to solve these problems, it is necessary to improve the standard of living of the villagers in every way.

On February 27, 2020, under the chairmanship of the President of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyev, a video selector meeting was held on measures aimed at reducing poverty through the development of entrepreneurship. Measures to reduce poverty through entrepreneurship development and vocational training were defined in it. "According to preliminary estimates, 12-15 percent or 4-5 million of our population are poor," he said.

President Shavkat Mirziyoyev. - This means that their daily income does not exceed 10-13 thousand soums. Or a family may have both a car and livestock, but if one person is seriously ill, at least 70 percent of the family's income goes to his treatment. So, can such a family be called complete? As the president, I am tormented every day by the question of what is happening to the vital needs of our people, such as food, treatment, education and clothing for their children," said Shavkat Mirziyoyev. , does not mean For this, first of all, it is necessary to train the population for a profession, increase their financial literacy, instill a sense of entrepreneurship in people, improve the infrastructure, educate their children, provide quality treatment, and introduce a system of address-based allowance payment," said the head of our state [1].

At the meeting, it was noted that first of all, it is necessary to analyze the actual conditions and situation at the level of each neighborhood, district, city, and region. For this, in the first direction, the real situation of poverty, that is, the collection of information about the number of low-income families in the neighborhoods, and in the second direction, the creation of a map of the district and city's potential, natural resources, land and infrastructure opportunities was determined. "We need to create all the conditions for people to work, become rich and live a good life," said the President.[2]

As it was mentioned, small industrial zones are established on unoccupied and non-agricultural areas around well-developed entrepreneurship and densely populated areas. Land plots in them are sold to entrepreneurs. Disused land will be distributed to the poor. Reducing poverty by training the population in entrepreneurship and improving their professional skills is the most important issue. Currently, there are about 1 million 400 thousand women and young people who are not officially employed in the country. The unemployment rate among women is 13 percent, and among young people is 15 percent. At the same time, today there is a need for 104,000 specialists in construction, 71,000 in the utility sector, 68,000 in the service sector, and 46,000 in light industry. At the meeting, it was emphasized that it is necessary to provide qualified specialists to the places where there is such a demand, to organize courses for training unemployed people in entrepreneurship in each region in order to ensure employment.

Vocational training courses are organized for single women and women with many children, unemployed people who want to study for a profession, in trades that are in high demand in everyday life, in particular, tailoring, cooking, hairdressing and other areas. Active involvement of non-governmental organizations in the establishment of vocational training centers, holding a competition for the best vocational training program among them, and awarding grants from the Employment Assistance Fund to the winners. We believe that if these assignments and tasks are fulfilled, the situation in our villages will improve, and the socio-economic situation of young people will undergo positive changes.

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